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The Risk of Poverty in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2021

It grew by an average of 10.07% between 2004 and 2021

Istat calculates the risk of poverty. The risk of poverty is defined as the percentage of people living in households with a net equivalised income below a poverty risk threshold set at 60% of the median of the individual distribution of net equivalised income. The income reference year is the calendar year preceding the survey year. The available historical series ranges from 2004 to 2021. The data refers to the Italian regions and macro-regions.

Ranking of the regions by value of the risk of poverty in 2021. Sicily is in first place by value of the risk of poverty in 2021 with a value of 38.1%, followed by Campania with a value of 37.60%, and by Calabria with a value of 33.2%. In the middle of the table are Lazio with a value of 20.6%, followed by Liguria with a value of 17.8%, and Piedmont and Veneto with 13.7%. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with a value of 9.6%, followed by Valle d'Aosta and Marche with a value of 8.00%.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in the risk of poverty between 2004 and 2021. Abruzzo is in first place for percentage change in the risk of poverty between 2004 and 2021 with a value equal to 64.88% passing from an amount of 16.8 units up to 27.7 units or equal to an amount of 10.9 units. Veneto follows with a percentage change in the risk of poverty between 2004 and 2021 equal to a value of 39.79% corresponding to a change from an amount of 9.89 units up to 13.7 units equal to a value of 3.9 units. Below is Sardinia with a variation equal to 37.62% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 20.2 units up to a value of 27.8 units or equal to +7.6 units.

In the middle of the table is Friuli Venezia Giulia with a variation equal to 21.11% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9 units up to 10.9 units equal to a variation of 1.9 units. Emilia Romagna with a variation equal to 11.62% corresponding to a variation from 8.6 units up to 9.6 units. Trentino Alto Adige follows with a variation equal to 11.36% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 8.8 units up to a value of 9.8 units.

Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a variation equal to -15.78% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 9.5 units up to 8 units equal to -1.5 units. Puglia follows with a variation equal to -16.44% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 30.4 units up to 25.4 units equal to -5 units. The Marche region is in last place in terms of the value of the change in the poverty risk value with an amount of -31.03% corresponding to a change from 11.6 units up to 8 units.

Poverty risk in the Italian macro-regions between 2004 and 2021. The poverty risk in Northern Italy grew from an amount of 10.3% in 2004 up to 12.5% in 2021 or a variation of 2.20 units equal to 21.36%. The poverty risk in the North-West grew from a value of 11.1% in 2004 to a value of 13.2% in 2021 or equal to an amount of 2.10 units equal to a value of 18.92%. The risk of poverty in the

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North-East grew by 25.00% starting from an amount of 9.2% up to a value of 11.5% or equal to 2.30 units corresponding to a variation of 25.00%. The risk of poverty in Central Italy grew by 17.91%, going from an amount of 13.4 units to a value of 15.8 units or equal to an amount of 2.40 units. The value of the risk of poverty in the South grew by 1.22%, going from an amount of 32.7% in 2004 to a value of 33.1% in 2021, i.e. equal to a variation of 0.4 units. The risk of poverty in Southern Italy grew by 0.63%, going from an amount of 31.8% in 2004 to a value of 32.00% in 2021, or a variation equal to an amount of 0.20 units. The risk of poverty in the Islands grew by 2.01%, going from an amount of 34.8% in 2004 to a value of 35.5% in 2021, or an amount equal to 0.70 units.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we consider clustering with the k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Two clusters are identified:

- Cluster 1: Veneto, Lombardy, Piedmont, Tuscany, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Emilia Romagna, Marche, Trentino Alto Adige, Umbria, Liguria, Valle d'Aosta, Lazio, Abruzzo;
- Cluster 2: Calabria, Campania, Basilicata, Sicily, Puglia, Molise, Sardinia.

From the point of view of clustering we can therefore note that from the point of view of the average, Cluster 2 dominates Cluster 1, i.e.: $C2 > C1$. That is, the regions of the South tend to have much higher poverty risk values than the regions of Northern Italy. However, we can note that the only region of Southern Italy to be present among the regions of Northern Italy is Abruzzo.

Conclusions. We can note that the value of the risk of poverty grew on average in the Italian regions by 10.07% between 2004 and 2021, going from an amount of 17.97 to a value of 19.78, or a variation equal to an amount of 1.81 units. However, even if the value of the poverty risk grew in percentage terms especially in the central-northern regions between 2004 and 2021, from the point of view of absolute values we can note that there is still a notable difference between the South and the northern regions. In fact, the risk of poverty in the southern regions is approximately 2.09 times that of the Centre, 2.51 times that of the North-West, 2.65 times that of the North, 2.88 times that of the North-East. It therefore follows that the population of the South is more exposed to economic and social risks. However, since social intervention policies have proven to be largely unsuccessful, as in the case of citizenship income and training courses for professional updating and for the unemployed, it is necessary to act to strengthen local labor markets. In fact, it is very likely that the only solution for reducing the risk of poverty is to introduce local labor markets, institutionalized with public-private tools for managing the supply-demand of labour, which are capable of reducing the risk of poverty through the job offer, adequate salaries and professional paths. It is therefore necessary that social policies return to being focused on work and on the issue of fair remuneration in order to resolve the issue of poverty.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange

for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

Rischio di Povertà nelle Regioni Italiane		
Rank	Regioni	2021
1	<i>Sicilia</i>	38,1
2	<i>Campania</i>	37,6
3	<i>Calabria</i>	33,2
4	<i>Molise</i>	29,3
5	<i>Sardegna</i>	27,8
6	<i>Abruzzo</i>	27,7
7	<i>Basilicata</i>	27,6
8	<i>Puglia</i>	25,4
9	<i>Lazio</i>	20,6
10	<i>Liguria</i>	17,8
11	<i>Piemonte</i>	13,7
12	<i>Veneto</i>	13,7
13	<i>Toscana</i>	12,4
14	<i>Lombardia</i>	12,3
15	<i>Umbria</i>	12,1
16	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	10,9
17	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	9,8
18	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	9,6
19	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	8
20	<i>Marche</i>	8

Rischio di Povertà nelle Regioni Italiane									
Regioni	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012
<i>Piemonte</i>	12,8	11,6	11,6	11,4	12,1	10,6	13,2	13,2	12,9
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	9,5	5,9	6,2	8,6	9	9,3	9,2	8,5	9,7
<i>Liguria</i>	13,3	15,3	13,9	15,3	14,4	10,4	11,1	12	14,3
<i>Lombardia</i>	10	9,5	10,6	11,2	10,3	10,3	10,7	9,5	9,1
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	8,8	7,5	6,2	6,2	6,8	7,9	7,6	9,4	10,7
<i>Veneto</i>	9,8	10,4	10,8	11,3	10,7	10,1	11,7	11,1	12
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	9	10,5	11,6	10	11,2	10,7	10,6	9,5	11,5
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	8,6	9,3	9,1	8,4	8,7	9,4	7,8	8,9	8,8
<i>Toscana</i>	9,6	9,4	8,6	9,2	9,2	9,6	11,5	12,4	11,4
<i>Umbria</i>	11,7	13,1	15,4	13,5	13	11,9	11,8	12,9	11,9
<i>Marche</i>	11,6	12,2	13,4	11,8	12,2	11	12,9	13,1	14,6
<i>Lazio</i>	16,8	16,3	16,1	16,2	15,1	15,9	15,9	17,2	19

<i>Abruzzo</i>	16,8	18	17,3	20,5	20	21,9	20,8	25,8	20,4
<i>Molise</i>	21,8	24,8	26,7	28,4	26,3	29	25	23,7	26,8
<i>Campania</i>	35,6	33,5	35,1	36,7	38,6	35,6	36,2	36,8	36,7
<i>Puglia</i>	30,4	33,9	35,1	31,8	27,7	27	27,4	30,3	29,6
<i>Basilicata</i>	27,8	30,6	28,5	29,8	30,2	32,9	25,9	31,1	32
<i>Calabria</i>	35,8	39	35	33,7	35,6	35,3	32,7	33,6	31,8
<i>Sicilia</i>	39,5	40,9	39,7	41,9	38,4	38,5	38,6	44,6	41,9
<i>Sardegna</i>	20,2	22,5	21,2	21,8	23,1	21,6	18,3	23	19,8
Regioni	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
<i>Piemonte</i>	11,1	13,8	11,9	14,2	14	14,2	13,4	13,5	13,7
<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	9,5	8,4	7	14,6	13,8	12	6,1		8
<i>Liguria</i>	15,6	16,6	15,9	14,8	13,7	14	13,4	16,3	17,8
<i>Lombardia</i>	8,4	9	11,1	13,3	13,6	11,1	12	11,4	12,3
<i>Trentino-Alto Adige</i>	9,3	7,7	8,3	11	9,4	12,3	8,7	9,9	9,8
<i>Veneto</i>	10,3	11,6	10,9	12,2	10,4	11	8,7	10,3	13,7
<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	9,8	9,2	8,2	9,2	9,3	8,2	8,4	14,6	10,9
<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	10,9	10,1	9,7	8,9	10,5	10,1	10,9	8,5	9,6
<i>Toscana</i>	12,1	11,6	9,6	9,6	12,9	14,4	14,3	14,1	12,4
<i>Umbria</i>	14,8	16,5	18,4	15,5	11,1	12,5	9,8	9,5	12,1
<i>Marche</i>	12,7	12,2	13,9	16	15,8	11,7	13,6	11,9	8
<i>Lazio</i>	18	18,5	20,5	21,8	20,1	19,3	17,2	19,4	20,6
<i>Abruzzo</i>	18,7	22	21,7	20,5	19,8	18,7	19,5	23,2	27,7
<i>Molise</i>	30,8	32,1	27,1	30,6	31	23,5	26,5	35,7	29,3
<i>Campania</i>	37,6	38,1	35,5	36,9	34,3	41,4	41,2	39,7	37,6
<i>Puglia</i>	29,6	25,8	30,3	27,4	26,2	26,8	30,4	25,9	25,4
<i>Basilicata</i>	33,1	25,6	28,1	27,7	27,9	30,1	27,1	36,5	27,6
<i>Calabria</i>	33,6	32,4	33,8	34,6	36,4	32,7	30,9	36	33,2
<i>Sicilia</i>	40,9	40,1	42,3	41,8	41,3	40,7	41,4	38,2	38,1
<i>Sardegna</i>	21,3	25,9	25,5	26,4	29,6	27,1	22,9	28,6	27,8

